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Laser-plasma Interaction and Characterization

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Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Part I. Shadowgraphy and expansion velocity	1
2.1	Theory	1
2.1.1	Shadowgraphy	1
2.1.2	Expansion velocity of plasma	1
2.2	Experimental setup	2
2.2.1	Irradiance of the laser	3
2.2.2	Calibration	4
2.3	Results and analysis	5
3	Part II. Plasma spectroscopy	7
3.1	Theory	7
3.2	Experimental setup	7
3.2.1	Calibration	9
3.3	Results and analysis	11
4	Conclusion	13

List of Figures

1	One of the shadowgraphic images of the plasma obtained in this experiment. One can note the shape and the profile of the plasma.	2
2	Basic set-up for shadowgraphy. Taken from S. Bastiani-Ceccotti, "Diagnostics" (lecture slides, Laser-matter interaction, École Polytechnique, Palaiseau, November 2023).	2
3	Experimental setup. The experimental arrangement included a high-power Nd-YAG laser, along with a series of optical components and a CCD camera. Numbers are used to identify the different elements; see the text for description.	3
5	Typical plasma image and profile. a) shows one image of the plasma for a delay of 26 ns, three different measurements of size are identified, see text. b) Profile of the image, taken with <i>ImageJ</i> software.	5
4	Calibration images. These images were used to set up a scale ranging from pixels to millimeters.	5
6	Profile of a thin strip that covers X_t in Fig. 5 a).	6
7	Experimental data plot with six initial data points (Left), demonstrating an inadequate fit. Subsequent analysis revealed a lack of coherence with three data points, leading to their exclusion. The revised plot, excluding the discarded points, exhibits a more reasonable fit to the experimental data (Right).	7
8	Basic experimental setup for Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy. Taken from [1].	8
9	Experimental setup. (Left) The experimental arrangement included a high-power Nd-YAG laser, along with a series of optical components. The created plasma light was directed to the adjacent room for the spectrometry. (Right) The experimental arrangement consists of Na, and Hg lamps for calibrations, a spectrometer, and a CCD camera for image capturing.	8
10	Observed spectra for Na (Left) and Hg (Right). These images were used to set up a scale ranging from pixels to nanometers.	9
11	Analysed intensity profiles for the observed spectra for Na (Left) and Hg (Right) using <i>ImageJ</i>	10

12	The plot illustrates the experimental data points alongside a fitted linear regression curve. The linear model is characterized by a gradient of 0.3002 and an intercept of 321.48. The associated uncertainties are quantified with a gradient error of 0.003 and an intercept error of 2.400, providing insights into the precision of the linear fit.	10
13	Two different spectra observed for the generated plasma light.	11
14	Analysed intensity profiles for the observed spectra.	11

List of Tables

1	Summary table. The mean distance is tabulated in both Pixel units [Px] and millimeters [mm] across various delay times.	14
2	Set number corresponds to which group the line belongs to (this is done only for the purpose of recognition, left most lines are grouped as 1 whereas the right-most lines are labeled as 4.). The fourth column is the closest wavelength found on the NIST data set (see [2]). C-I means carbon minus one electron, similarly for C-II. .	15

1 Introduction

The objective of this experiment is to ascertain the ionization degree of laser-generated plasma formed on a carbon target, along with determining the plasma's expansion velocity. To accomplish these objectives, two distinct methods were employed: shadowgraphy and spectrometry, both widely utilized optical diagnostics in plasma studies. In the initial phase, we utilized shadowgraphy to calculate the expansion velocity, enabling subsequent determination of the ionization degree. In the subsequent phase, spectrometry was employed to directly measure the ionization degree, following which the expansion velocity was estimated. The results obtained from both methodologies are then compared.

2 Part I. Shadowgraphy and expansion velocity

2.1 Theory

2.1.1 Shadowgraphy

Shadowgraphy is widely employed for its simplicity and the ability to obtain plasma images, enabling qualitative evaluations of its shape and profile (See Figure 1). This technique is particularly useful for studying the dynamics of plasmas because it can visualize rapidly changing structures and provide information about the density, temperature, and flow velocity of the plasma. A basic schematic setup for shadowgraphy is presented in Figure 2, the plasma is created in a target and a laser probe impinges on it.

Recall that the path of a laser beam in a plasma is perturbed by absorption and refraction, which depend on the refractive index (which is a function of the electronic density). The shadow of the plasma is produced by the low frequencies, which are situated close to the optical axis and correspond to undeviated rays. In contrast, high frequencies are positioned far from the optical axis, corresponding to significantly refracted rays originating from regions with a high-density gradient, see Figure 2.

2.1.2 Expansion velocity of plasma

The expansion velocity of a plasma is how fast it spreads into its surroundings. It can be high, reaching kilometers per second in some cases. The actual speed depends on factors like plasma temperature, pressure, surrounding gas density, and external forces like magnetic fields. The blow-off velocity of plasma is approximately equal to the sound speed

Figure 1: One of the shadowgraphic images of the plasma obtained in this experiment. One can note the shape and the profile of the plasma.

Figure 2: Basic set-up for shadowgraphy. Taken from S. Bastiani-Ceccotti, "Diagnostics" (lecture slides, Laser-matter interaction, École Polytechnique, Palaiseau, November 2023).

at the critical density.

$$v \approx c_s = \left(\frac{z^* k_B T_e}{m_i} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (1)$$

For a given temperature, the measurement of v and T allows us to determine z^* .

2.2 Experimental setup

The experimental setup consisted of a high-power laser (Nd-YAG), with a set of optical elements and a CCD camera. This can be realized in Figure 3.

In Figure 3 numbers are used to identify the different elements. Number one represents the beam blocker, this element is used to block the laser beam when it is operational. Two is the beam splitter, which divides the laser beam in two, one continues to propagate towards the target (pump beam), and the other one is deviated and travels a longer distance before impinging on the target (probe beam). The probe beam is deviated using a series

Figure 3: Experimental setup. The experimental arrangement included a high-power Nd-YAG laser, along with a series of optical components and a CCD camera. Numbers are used to identify the different elements; see the text for description.

of mirrors (number 10). The distance it travels can be varied at will, by changing the positions of some of the mirrors (number 9) in the setup. This is equivalent to modifying the delay time. Plotting the delay time against the size of the plasma allows us to obtain the expansion velocity.

Number three is a divergent lens at (12 ± 1) cm from the beam splitter. Four identifies the convergence lenses, with respective focal lengths of (20.5 ± 1) cm and (15.5 ± 1) cm; the first convergent lens is (9 ± 1) cm away from the divergent lens. Five is an optical element that reduces the intensity of the laser, it is used, together with the beam blocker, when the laser is operational but no measurements are being taken. Number six is the target. Seven is a lens placed (15 ± 1) cm away from the target and (45 ± 1) cm away from the camera. Number eight is the CCD camera.

2.2.1 Irradiance of the laser

The irradiance of the laser is given by

$$I = \frac{E}{\tau S},$$

where E is the energy, τ the duration of the laser pulse, and S the area. To approximate S , we use the following expression,

$$S = \frac{1.22\lambda f}{D}, \quad (2)$$

Nd-YAG lasers are Q-switched to generate pulses typically ranging from 10 to 50 nanoseconds. Consequently, they produce a diffraction-limited spot size on the order of micrometers, with intensities on the material's surface in the range of $10^{10} - 10^{12}$ W/cm². In this experiment, assuming that 100 mJ is delivered within 35 nS, we calculated the intensity of the laser beam in the order of 10^{11} W/cm² which is parallel with the expected value. In equation 2 we used $\lambda = 1064$ nm, the wavelength of the laser; $f = 20.5$ cm, the focal length, and $D \approx 5$ cm.

A plasma is generated through the application of adequate energy to matter, leading to the ionization of atoms. This process can be accomplished using a laser, capable of ionizing through various mechanisms. Arranged in order of increasing laser intensity, the mechanisms include the photoelectric effect, multiphoton ionization, tunnel effect, and barrier suppression ionization. The following parameter separates multiphoton ionization from the tunnel effect:

$$\gamma = \omega_L \sqrt{\frac{2E_i}{I_L}}. \quad (3)$$

The case $\gamma > 1$ corresponds to multiphoton ionization, and $\gamma < 1$ to tunnel effect. In most situations, to get $\gamma = 1$ one requires $I \approx 10^{14}$ W/cm². Since γ is inversely proportional to I_L , if I_L decreases, γ increases. Thus, for $I \approx 10^{11}$ W/cm², we have $\gamma > 1$. The main mechanism of ionization is multiphoton ionization, which consists of the simultaneous absorption of several photons.

2.2.2 Calibration

The experimental setup allows us to get a series of images of the plasma expansion; to measure the size of the plasma, we need to set up a scale from pixel to centimeters. The experimental setup allows us to change the position of the target with respect to a fixed camera, knowing the size of the images (1024×768) and the distance that the target was moved, we can get the aforementioned scale. In Fig. 4 we can see the two images used for calibration. Analyzing the provided images, it was observed that 1.4 mm corresponds to 614 pixels. Subsequently, one pixel corresponds to a distance of $(2.28 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-6}$ m—establishing the calibration ratio for the experiment.

Figure 5: Typical plasma image and profile. a) shows one image of the plasma for a delay of 26 ns, three different measurements of size are identified, see text. b) Profile of the image, taken with *ImageJ* software.

Figure 4: Calibration images. These images were used to set up a scale ranging from pixels to millimeters.

2.3 Results and analysis

As mentioned earlier, the experimental configuration allows us to modify the delay time. Six distinct delay times were employed, and for each, multiple images were captured.

In Fig. 5 a) we present a typical image of the plasma. To obtain its size, we must identify the border of the target. To achieve this, the profile of a thin strip of the image was studied using the *ImageJ* software (See Fig. 5 b)). Notice that there is a sharp drop in the profile after a certain maximum, the position border was defined as this maximum. In this particular image, the value is 744 pixels. The position of the border was identified for each delay time.

Figure 6: Profile of a thin strip that covers X_t in Fig. 5 a).

In Fig. 5 a) we see that the length of the plasma can be defined in several ways. We define it as the average of X_t and X_b . The case with the average of X_t , X_b , and X_m was also studied, nevertheless, the results were less satisfactory. To estimate X_t the profile of a thin strip was plotted, see Fig. 6. In this image we see an increase of the intensity followed by a small drop and then a steeper drop; comparing the profile with the plasma image we concluded that the plasma begins before the first drop, the maximum before it was chosen as the beginning of the plasma. This is an arbitrary choice, the plasma starts somewhere around this position, thus, there is a considerable error in this measurement. Since we know the target's position, we can subtract the position where the plasma begins to get the plasma's size. The procedure was repeated for X_b and each image. However, it must be pointed out that the profile is different in each case.

The results are summarized in Table 1. Then, the distance of the plasma expansion (in pixel units) was plotted against the corresponding delay time as shown in Figure 7. The gradient of the plot was determined as (10.75 ± 1.02) pixel/nS. Using the calibration ratio calculated earlier, the expansion velocity of the plasma was determined as

$$(2.45 \pm 0.23) \times 10^4 \text{ m/s}. \quad (4)$$

From the previous value, and knowing the temperature of the plasma, it is possible to estimate the value of z^* in equation 1. From [3] we estimated a temperature of 80 eV (for more details see section 3.3), thus $z^* = 0.93 \approx 1$.

Figure 7: Experimental data plot with six initial data points (Left), demonstrating an inadequate fit. Subsequent analysis revealed a lack of coherence with three data points, leading to their exclusion. The revised plot, excluding the discarded points, exhibits a more reasonable fit to the experimental data (Right).

3 Part II. Plasma spectroscopy

3.1 Theory

In atomic emission spectroscopy atoms are excited to a high energy level, then, they decay releasing the excitation energy. This energy is well-defined for each specific atom. In laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), a focused laser beam is used to produce a plasma (composed of excited species of the sample) on the surface of solid and liquid samples. It can be used for the characterization of materials, since each excited atom emits a unique set of spectral lines, particularly in the optical region of the spectrum. The emission can be collected and analyzed to determine the chemical composition of the sample. A LIBS plasma can be formed as a single event with just one laser pulse or using repetitive laser pulses.

Compared to conventional emission spectroscopy, LIBS atomizes only a small portion of the sample by a focused laser pulse, which produces a spark in the sample. Due to the short life of the spark emission, capturing the light is a challenge. The main components of LIBS are illustrated in Figure 8.

3.2 Experimental setup

The experimental configuration was set up in a way such that it closely mirrored the arrangement of the first part to ensure consistency and reliability of the results. However,

Figure 8: Basic experimental setup for Laser-Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy. Taken from [1].

some changes were needed. Instead of directly placing the CCD camera after a lens and the target, a different lens was used to focus the light generated by the plasma into the contiguous room (See Figure 3). The lens was placed very close to the target to collect the light before it diverges; a short focal length is enough for this purpose. In Figure 9 the hole in the wall leading to the next room can be seen.

Figure 9: Experimental setup. (Left) The experimental arrangement included a high-power Nd-YAG laser, along with a series of optical components. The created plasma light was directed to the adjacent room for the spectrometry. (Right) The experimental arrangement consists of Na, and Hg lamps for calibrations, a spectrometer, and a CCD camera for image capturing.

In this room, a lens with a big diameter (around 10 cm) and focal length (around 45 cm) was used to capture as much light as possible. Then, a mirror was utilized to send the light into the slit of a prism spectrometer. The lens and mirror were aligned and placed in such a way that the light was focused approximately 2 cm inside the slit of the spectrometer. This tool has a diaphragm that allows it to regulate the quantity of light that it captures. The

apparatus has the purpose of separating light into its different wavelengths with the help of two prisms; at the exit, there is an aperture that allows viewing the resulting spectrum. A ruler was placed below to make sure the spectral lines were formed in the same position and were not displaced with regards to the calibration (see Figure 10).

A CCD camera was placed facing the aperture of the spectrometer. It should be noted that the camera should be placed at the right angle at the appropriate position to collect the light coming from the apparatus. Otherwise, the camera will receive very little light, and the images will have poor quality. Additionally, several parameters of the camera can be adjusted (gain, exposure time, etc.) to improve the images. Since the repetition rate of our laser system was one hertz, the exposure time chosen was one second, which allowed us to collect all the information coming from the plasma.

It should be also noted that it may be necessary to rotate or displace the target after prolonged exposure to the laser. This precaution is essential as the target could undergo damage during extended exposure, potentially influencing the final spectrum.

3.2.1 Calibration

Figure 10: Observed spectra for Na (Left) and Hg (Right). These images were used to set up a scale ranging from pixels to nanometers.

A mercury (Hg) and a sodium (Na) lamp were used to calibrate the system. They were placed next to the spectrometer (see Figure 9 (Right)). Images of the resulting spectrum were taken with the CCD camera, see Figure 10. The *imageJ* software was used to obtain the profile of the images (Figure 11). In the profiles we can identify three peaks (or lines) for the Na lamp and four for the Hg lamp, we can give the position of each peak in pixel units. Given that these lamps are very well-studied, the wavelengths of the spectral lines,

and their relative intensity, are known (see [4, 5, 6]), then, it is possible to associate each peak the corresponding wavelength. Thus, by plotting the position against wavelength for each peak we can obtain an expression that allows us to go from position to wavelength, this is done in Figure 12.

Figure 11: Analysed intensity profiles for the observed spectra for Na (Left) and Hg (Right) using *ImageJ*.

According to the calibration curve (see Figure 12), it was determined that one pixel corresponds to 0.3002 nm (using the gradient) with a positive offset of 321.48 nm (using the intercept).

Figure 12: The plot illustrates the experimental data points alongside a fitted linear regression curve. The linear model is characterized by a gradient of 0.3002 and an intercept of 321.48. The associated uncertainties are quantified with a gradient error of 0.003 and an intercept error of 2.400, providing insights into the precision of the linear fit.

3.3 Results and analysis

Figure 13: Two different spectra observed for the generated plasma light.

Several images of the plasma spectrum were taken, see Figure 13. Two of the displayed spectra were used to encompass all discernible lines available for extraction. Notice that the spectral lines are clustered in different sets, this is more evident when plotting the respective intensity profiles (Figure 14), we can see four groups where we can identify several spectral lines. Using the calibration curve, we can associate a wavelength to each of these lines. Moreover, the NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) atomic spectra database lines [2] provide the different observed wavelengths in the air of the spectral lines of different ions. Thus, comparing the wavelengths of the experiment with those of the database we can identify the resulting ions. The results are summarized in Table 2. We can conclude that our plasma is made of two ions, C-I and C-II, 62.5% of the former and 37.5% of the latter.

Figure 14: Analysed intensity profiles for the observed spectra.

In the article [3], the authors measured the electron temperature in a laser-produced plasma with laser intensity between 2×10^{11} and 5×10^{12} W/cm². One of the targets used was carbon, they found a maximum temperature of 330 eV. Additionally, they plotted the temperature as a function of the intensity. Although they don't have data points for a laser intensity of 2×10^{11} W/cm², we can extrapolate their results for this value. The result is a temperature of 80 eV. It was not possible to extrapolate the temperature for the case of 1×10^{11} W/cm². For an intensity of 1×10^{12} , we can interpolate a temperature of 160 eV.

In Section 2.2.1, we estimated an irradiance of the laser of the order of 10^{11} W/cm², from [3] which corresponds to a temperature between 80 and 160 eV. An interesting remark made by the researchers is that the carbon can be considered fully ionized at temperatures greater than 200 eV. Moreover, at temperatures of about 100 eV, 8% of the carbon ions will be fully ionized. From both observations and the fact that we found mostly C-I ions, it is more likely that the electron temperature of the plasma is around 80 eV.

With the temperature provided, the expansion velocity of the plasma can be estimated using Equation 1, and a comparison can be made with the value obtained in the initial phase of the experiment. This will be a very rough estimation due to the presence of many assumptions and sources of uncertainty. Assuming that the plasma is composed only of C-I, the expansion velocity is

$$v = 25350.500 \text{ m/s}$$

The value falls within the uncertainty interval of Equation 4. Consistency is observed in our results.

It should be mentioned that the closest wavelength in the NIST dataset was assigned to the measured values. However, taking into account the error of the measurement (around 3 nm), it could be the case that some wavelengths were wrongly assigned. For example, for the 437.656 nm line, there was another one in the dataset with a 437.1381 nm wavelength corresponding to C-I. Thus, the proportion of ions may be different. In fact, three wavelengths of Table 2 could have been assigned to C-I instead of C-II. Furthermore, if we take a weighted average for z^* , with the proportions found originally, instead of assuming a plasma composed of mainly C-I ions, we get $v = 29726.096$ m/s. This value doesn't fit in the uncertainty interval of Equation 4, thus, the plasma is mainly composed of C-I ions with a proportion higher than 62.5%.

4 Conclusion

The expansion velocity of a laser-generated plasma was estimated with two different methods. The values obtained are consistent. Additionally, it was determined that the plasma is mainly composed of C-I ions in a proportion higher than 62.5%. These results are highly dependent on the value of the temperature of the plasma estimated, which was extrapolated from [3]. To have a better estimation of the expansion velocity, we suggest modifying the experimental setup to also measure the plasma temperature. Additionally, we suggest taking more images of the spectrum of the plasma to have a better estimation of the different wavelengths, so that they could be assigned more precisely to a given ion.

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Delay [ns]	Image	Distance [Px]	Average distance [Px]	Average distance [mm]
12.10	1	90.67	106.00	0.24618
	2	102.00		
	5	99.00		
15.30	1	99.00	100.50	0.22914
	2	109.50		
	3	102.50		
	4	91.00		
17.68	1	115.00	114.87	0.26192
	2	114.00		
	3	113.00		
	4	117.50		
20.84	1	110.00	111.62	0.25451
	2	110.00		
	3	114.50		
	4	112.00		
23.34	2	111.50	106.17	0.24206
	3	99.00		
	5	108.00		
26.30	1	209.00	212.00	0.48336
	2	221.00		
	3	206.00		

Table 1: Summary table. The mean distance is tabulated in both Pixel units [Px] and millimeters [mm] across various delay times.

Set number	Wavelength (Pixel units)	Wavelength [nm]	Wavelength [nm] (NIST)	Ion
1	377	434.654	434.4309	C-I
1	387	437.656	437.6562	C-II
1	397	440.658	440.9161	C-II
1	411	444.861	446.1300	C-I
2	600	501.600	501.7090	C-I
2	614	505.803	505.7682	C-I
2	630	510.606	510.7910	C-II
3	752	547.232	547.8590	C-II
3	763	550.534	550.8510	C-I
3	777	554.737	554.7271	C-I
3	792	559.240	559.7300	C-I
3	809	564.343	564.2770	C-I
4	888	588.060	587.7310	C-I
4	897	590.761	590.7210	C-II
4	904	592.863	591.9450	C-II
4	911	594.964	595.0040	C-I

Table 2: Set number corresponds to which group the line belongs to (this is done only for the purpose of recognition, left most lines are grouped as 1 whereas the right-most lines are labeled as 4.). The fourth column is the closest wavelength found on the NIST data set (see [2]). C-I means carbon minus one electron, similarly for C-II.